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Instructional Competence and Multicultural Challenges of Filipino Science Teachers in Thai Schools Towards the Development of an Intervention Program

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Abstract

This study examined instructional competence and multicultural challenges of Filipino science teachers in Thai schools. As the demand for Filipino science teachers was rising in Thailand because of their English proficiency and their knowledge in science, the study was conducted to determine the effectiveness of Filipino teachers in teaching science in a multicultural environment. The descriptive-quantitative design was used, which included 101 samples of Filipino science teachers working in the public/government, private, and international schools in Thailand. A researcher-made questionnaire was used to collect data by evaluating the instructional competence of the participant and also identifying the challenges that they faced in a multicultural environment. The data were analyzed using descriptive and inferential statistical tools, such as frequency, percentage, weighted mean, t-test, ANOVA, and Pearson's r. Findings revealed that Filipino science teachers displayed high competence in using the English language and integration of current trends and pedagogy, but a moderate level of competence in incorporating Thai culture in teaching science. However, major challenges persisted, particularly regarding language barriers, cultural adaptation, and professional development. Correlation analysis confirmed a significant relationship between instructional competence and the multicultural challenges encountered. Findings suggested the significance of intervention programs, where cultural orientation, language support, and ongoing professional development could be applied to enhance the instructional competency of the Filipino science teachers in Thailand. Finally, the study contained evidence-based suggestions to educational institutions and policymakers on how to enhance support mechanisms to enable foreign science teachers to succeed in various learning settings.

Keywords: instructional competence, multicultural challenges, Filipino science teachers, Thai schools, pedagogical approaches

1 Introduction

Science education in a globalized world is a cornerstone of national development. It prompts innovation, creative thinking, and scientific literacy required in solving universal challenges. The role of qualified science educators has gained much significance as many countries strive to enhance their science instruction. Effective science education can lead

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to the creation of globally competent learners. Hence, the study of determining the factors that affect the delivery of science education remains a current priority area of research in education.

Teachers' migration in recent years has become a way of addressing the shortages of teachers and the increased need for good education across the world. According to UNESCO (2024), there is a shortage of primary and secondary educators worldwide, and international recruitment of teachers is a way of filling these shortages. Some countries have relied on international teachers to address the shortage of educators in specific fields, like science education. The movement of teachers crossing another border has reformed the classroom settings and provided multicultural learning spaces. Migration of the teachers has also shown the importance of determining the effects of cross-cultural experiences on the performance of the teaching. As a result, the issue of investigating the efficiency of foreign teachers in different educational systems is gaining popularity.

The Philippines has emerged as one of the suppliers of educators in foreign countries, as a result of the perceived competency of the graduates of education courses. Filipino teachers are also known for their mastery of the English language, flexibility, and subject knowledge. Due to this, Filipino teachers are highly in demand in other countries such as Thailand, especially for those courses that are taught in English. During 2019, there were already twenty-three thousand (23,000) Filipino migrant teachers in Thailand teaching in different educational systems (Dumlao & Tepsuriwong, 2019, as cited in Grumo & Siriwato, 2024). The growing popularity of hiring Filipino teachers in Thailand is due to their capabilities in delivering instruction and teaching in the English language. However, there is a lack of studies that examine the experiences of Filipino science teachers in foreign classrooms using quantitative data.

The English Program (EP) has been implemented in Thailand's educational system, both in public and private schools. According to Sailabada and Soontornwipast (2024), Thailand's educational reform goal is to enhance the students' competency in the English language, and this is achieved through English Programs that use English as a medium of instruction in some core subjects, including science. This goal requires a number of teachers who can teach science in the English language; many of these came from the Philippines. While the intent was to enhance the students' learning using English instruction, problems arose, such as language, cultural alignment, and limited professional development. Teacher competence can be best analyzed by understanding the instructional environment in these programs.

Filipino science teachers in schools in Thailand play a key role in providing science education to their students. Using English as the language of instruction, they are tasked with presenting scientific concepts in an understandable and impactful manner. Their presence contributes to the attainment of Thailand's vision of internationalizing its education system. Although they make a lot of contributions, they are likely to experience multicultural challenges that can influence their performance in class. Therefore, it is important to understand and investigate the factors that influence the teaching competence of teachers.

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A complex set of challenges arises for teachers teaching in foreign countries, and it may affect instruction. Filipino teachers need to cope with language barriers, unfamiliar education systems, new cultural demands, and limited professional development that might be different from those that existed in their home country. These aspects need constant adjustment, at professional and personal levels. When dealing with these challenges, it can impact the classroom delivery and student learning outcomes. It is crucial to measure these variables as they can provide an idea of how they affect teaching competence.

In many forms of communication inside the school or institution, language is an important tool to create an effective teaching and learning process, especially in today's generation. According to Nilsson (2022), an effective language that is used in the classroom can enhance students' motivation, confidence, and oral engagement, thereby improving the overall teaching and learning experience of the learners. Many educational institutions in Thailand already use English as a medium, but it still poses a great barrier for Filipino teachers in terms of language, which affects their easy communication with students. A study revealed that the average English proficiency level among students in Thailand was A1, which is an indication of a basic user level. This study suggests that most of the students have limited English proficiency, and this can affect effective communication and learning inside the classroom (Phong-a-ran et al., 2020). Language barrier may affect classroom management, delivery of the lesson, assessing the students' learning, and the creation of good relationships with the learners. Understanding how these language barriers affect teaching is very important, as it can improve the Filipino teachers' teaching competence as well as establish frameworks that create a more supportive educational system and setting.

Thailand is known for its unique and vibrant culture, and they are often considered a great culture because of its rich traditions and distinctive way of life. Cultural nuances have an important role in shaping classroom dynamics and educational practices. A study underscores the necessity for educators to integrate cultural awareness into their teaching practices because this will help in fostering a more engaging and effective learning environment (Khamouja et al., 2020). The teachers teaching in the Filipino context with the Philippines' cultural and educational system have to change and adapt to the Thai cultural setting. These changes and adaptations entail managing diverse student behavior, expectations regarding authority and discipline, and varying levels of classroom participation. By exploring the techniques that Filipino teachers use to manage cultural differences, we can understand how to increase effective multiculturalism and recognize which aspects can be helpful to enhance the teaching effectiveness of teachers.

Besides the classroom-specific concerns, the foremost concerns of Filipino science teachers working in Thailand are the limited access to professional development, such as seminars, workshops, and formal training programs. According to the National Math and Science Initiative (2023), students with a teacher who participated in well-designed professional development programs have better achievements and graduation rates. For a specialized field like science education, where the curriculum and technological integration continue to progress, professional development is essential, as it helps educators to remain updated on the latest strategies, content knowledge, and pedagogical trends. Unfortunately, many Filipino science teachers in Thailand often find themselves without

institutional support or resources to attend meaningful training (Arsenue & Espiritu, 2024). Due to administrative priorities, some schools may not offer regular in-service training or support teachers in attending external workshops. The availability and effect of professional development should be assessed to understand the presence of professional development in influencing the effectiveness of teaching.

Teaching competence can be defined as the ability of the teacher to facilitate learning in a clear, organized, and engaging manner. Through student outcomes, classroom observations, and teacher self-evaluation, teaching competence can be assessed. In an international context, language, culture, and professional support are external variables that can also assess teaching competence. To provide a more comprehensive evaluation of the performance of teachers, these variables must be considered, too. Studies among foreign educators are thus required to be holistic in nature.

This study wanted to dig deeper by exploring teaching competence beyond conventional metrics. This study attempted to create a more comprehensive portrait of the experiences of Filipino science teachers by understanding the multicultural challenges they faced, such as language barriers, cultural adaptation, and professional development, and to understand their relationship to their teaching competence. These are variables that are real, measurable, and are part of teaching in Thai schools. It should be quantitatively analyzed to understand its impact on the performance of teaching so as to educate all the stakeholders. Collective analysis of these variables assists in improving knowledge of the effectiveness of teaching in multicultural contexts.

1.1 Statement of the Problem

This study aims to assess the level of instructional competence and the multicultural challenges of Filipino Teachers in Thai schools towards the development of an intervention program to enhance their instructional competence.

This study seeks to attain the following specific objectives:

1. What is the profile of the Filipino science teachers in terms of:
 - 1.1. Age
 - 1.2. Sex
 - 1.3. Type of school
 - 1.4. Number of teaching experiences in Thai Schools
2. What is the level of instructional competence among the respondents when teaching science, along the following dimensions:
 - 2.1. English Use
 - 2.2. Thai culture Integration
 - 2.3. Application of Current Pedagogies
3. What are the multicultural challenges encountered by the respondents in terms of:
 - 3.1. Language Barrier
 - 3.1.1. Classroom management
 - 3.1.2. Students' participation
 - 3.1.3. Delivery of the lesson
 - 3.1.4. Evaluating students' learning

3.2. Cultural Adaptation

- 3.2.1. Classroom Expectations
- 3.2.2. Teaching Approaches
- 3.2.3. Nonverbal cues

3.3. Professional Development

- 3.3.1. Job satisfaction
- 3.3.2. Motivation
- 3.3.3. Retention

4. Is there a significant difference in the level of instructional competence of the respondents when grouped according to their profile?
5. Is there a significant difference in the multicultural challenges encountered by the respondents when grouped according to their profile?
6. Is there a significant relationship between the level of instructional competence among the respondents and the challenges encountered?
7. Based on the results of the study, what intervention may be proposed to address the instructional competence and challenges faced by Filipino science teachers in Thailand?

2 Methods

2.1 Research Design

This study employed a quantitative research design that was appropriate for its nature and objectives, which sought to investigate the multicultural challenges faced by Filipino science teachers in Thai schools, such as language barriers, cultural adaptation, and professional development, and to identify if these challenges had a relationship to the teaching competence of the teachers. The quantitative method was more dependable since it relied on statistics and methods that could be created and shared objectively within academia. According to Enago Academy (2022), quantitative research takes a systematic method, analyzing data to determine the link between variables. It used computational, statistical, and mathematical methods to obtain findings. Quantitative research was critical in this study because it enabled the researcher to measure and analyze data numerically using statistical methods. With this method, the results were of reliable, generalized, and non-biased research since the conclusions were made based on the statistical findings as opposed to a personal understanding.

The study entailed the use of a descriptive study approach. Being descriptive research, it collected specific and factual information with which to describe observed events (McCombes, 2023). The descriptive studies were undertaken to acquire an improved comprehension of a phenomenon, circumstance, or population. Unlike other studies, in descriptive studies, there was no control or manipulation of study variables. The sole educational aim was the observation and measurement of the variables in order to know more about them.

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2.2 Participants

The total number of respondents who were selected to be part of the study was 101 Filipino national science teachers who were working at schools in Thailand. The method was a total enumeration (census) of the target population; therefore, the sample size was equal to the total population ($N = 101$). The researcher chose Filipino science teachers as respondents to explore their unique experiences and multicultural challenges within the Thai educational system, particularly concerning language, culture, and professional development. Filipino science teachers working in Thai schools formed an important and well-appreciated section of the foreign teachers, and they were instrumental in meeting the demand for English-speaking teachers, especially in the field of science. They were observed in many educational institutions such as international schools, private schools, and even government/public schools. The selection of the respondents was made on certain specifications that are meant to ensure that they are personally relevant and have the capacity to give information-rich data that is relevant in line with the objectives of the research. Main peculiarities of the respondents were: (1) The respondents were of Filipino nationality and currently teaching in Thailand, (2) The respondents were teaching science subjects, (3) The respondents were using the English language as a medium of instruction, and (4) The respondents had at least a minimum of one year of teaching experience in Thai classrooms. The combination of these characteristics ensured that the respondents were well placed to give informed, relevant, and meaningful data to the study, the aim of which was to determine the relationship between their challenges in school and their teaching competence.

2.3 Instrumentation

The instrument that was utilized in the study was a self-made questionnaire. To identify the level of instructional competence among science teachers, a structured survey questionnaires were utilized as an instrument. The researcher used checklist-type questionnaires answerable by Not Competent (1), Slightly Competent (2), Competent (3), and Highly Competent (4). To identify the multicultural challenges encountered by Filipino science teachers in Thailand upon teaching in terms of language barrier, cultural adaptation, and professional development, structured survey questionnaires were utilized as an instrument. The researcher used a checklist-type questionnaire answerable by Strongly Disagree (1), Disagree (2), Agree (3), Strongly Agree (4). To ensure the quality, relevance, and accuracy of the research instrument in measuring the intended variables, validation and reliability testing were conducted.

2.4 Data gathering and Analysis

Using purposive and convenience sampling, the researcher identified potential respondents. Communication was conducted through email, messaging app, and teacher

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networks for the Filipino science teachers who met the inclusion criteria. Then the questionnaire was finalized and turned into a Google Form and distributed to the respondents. The form included a cover letter stating what the study is all about and an informed consent statement. The respondents were selected, and links to the form were sent to them. The respondents were given two weeks to a month to fill in the questionnaire. The researcher used follow-up reminders in order to prompt timely responses and boost the response rate during this period. Once the data collection period ended, all valid responses were downloaded and tabulated in a spreadsheet form and were ready to be screened. The researcher also ensured that the data was complete and accurate. Finally, the statistical analysis of the data gathered was conducted. Relevant statistical instruments were chosen to analyze the findings and get results concerning the aims of the research.

2.5 Ethical Considerations

At the very start of the online questionnaire, a short introduction was given, which also contained a consent statement, explaining the freedom of choice regarding participation in the study. The respondents who were allowed to proceed with the survey were those who acknowledged and agreed to the consent. The study was completely voluntary. There was neither coercion nor pressure exerted to persuade participation. The respondents were free to refuse their participation and/or to leave the study at any moment without consequences. All the respondents were made anonymous. No personal identification details were requested through the questionnaire. Confidentiality of all the responses was upheld, and their application was limited to the application of this academic research. Each piece of information collected was managed in an accountable way. The data collected were not fabricated, manipulated, or misrepresented, and the researcher ensured the data were reported in the way they were obtained. The findings and the results were tabulated and shown in an objective light, and the conclusions were evidence-based.

3 Results and Discussion

3.1 Profile of the respondents

The majority of the respondents were male Filipino science teachers (51.5%), and females made up (48.5%). The majority of them were also between the ages of 25 and 39, which constituted (83.2%) of the sample. A large proportion (72.3%) of them taught in public schools, and most (68.3%) of them had less than five years of teaching experience in Thailand.

3.2 Level of Instructional Competence

The study revealed that the respondents were good at speaking fluent English, posing clear questions to confirm the students' comprehension, and involving students in discussions. These areas represented high levels of communication skills, which were necessary in achieving an interactive and supportive learning environment. Nomnian et al. (2023) claimed that Filipino teachers were valued because they used active and communicative teaching techniques that successfully helped not only to engage students but also to improve their English language skills. It was demonstrated as well that Filipino teachers were characterized as possessing exceptionally good communication skills in the English language (Nanez & Viray, 2023). However, the data also shows that although respondents were competent in using proper grammar in the English language when learning science, it was the field that also needed attention. It was noted that non-native English teachers, even though they were proficient in the English language, tended to have problems with grammatical mistakes (Utami & Mahardika, 2023).

The study also revealed that respondents possessed competence across several critical aspects of teaching science. Notably, they were skilled in terms of integrating local Thai environmental issues into classroom discussions, encouraging students to share cultural experiences related to science, and using Thai cultural examples when explaining scientific concepts. Such practices underscore their capacity to make science lessons meaningful and more interesting to Thai learners by relating the cultural contexts of the learners to the science lessons to enhance the level of engagement and understanding during science education (Ganesan, 2025). Teachers can contribute to closing the gap between theory and the real experience of students by placing abstract science-related concepts in the context of familiar cultural frames, contributing to a better understanding (Pomat et al., 2024). Studies also attested that student engagement and academic performance in STEM subjects could be promoted through the use of culturally relevant educational content (Edilo et al., 2022). This pedagogical approach had not only positive effects on the academic performance of students but also on their overall development. The use of cultural elements in lessons fostered cultural competence, social awareness, and positive interaction skills, which were needed in the setting of a multicultural classroom (Galut, 2025). On the other hand, the study also shows the areas in which the respondents had only a slight competence. In particular, they were less effective at applying Thai folklore or cultural stories

to explain natural science concepts and at using language features of Thai words in an appropriate way to supplement the teaching of science. This finding was in line with the studies that indicate that teachers, although recognizing the importance of cultural integration, faced difficulties in applying culturally specific pedagogical practices. Lack of resources and training were among the factors that inhibited the successful application of local stories and traditional knowledge to science learning (Susilawati et al., 2024).

The study also shows that the respondents were quite highly competent in a number of areas in teaching science. They exhibited specific strengths in terms of their ability to efficiently use technology, including PowerPoint presentations, educational videos, and quizzes online, to aid teaching. This result corresponds to other studies, which indicated that the integration of technology, particularly visual representation and conceptualization, had a substantial positive effect on the pedagogical efficiency in various learning systems (Cheng et al., 2021). Besides their technological aptitude, the respondents were good at providing real-life issues in science teaching and used inquiry-based learning methodology to encourage critical thinking using practical learning of science. The practices were indicative of their experience in using contemporary pedagogical practices that focused on active tasks, problem-solving, and student-centered education, which was necessary to promote higher-order thinking skills (Kang et al., 2020). Overall, this competence implied that respondents have a good base of modern practices of teaching science that focus on student engagement and the practical use of scientific knowledge (Madsen et al., 2023). However, the data also pointed to the areas where the respondents were competent, although not at the top of their abilities. They can employ virtual laboratories or simulations by using technology and differentiate instruction to meet the needs of the diverse students. Though these competencies are clear, some studies suggested the possibility of future professional learning, specifically, how to work with more sophisticated digital tools and how to better customize the instruction to the profile of individual students (Paje et al., 2021).

The study revealed that respondents were highly competent in the use of English as well as the application of current pedagogies in teaching science. Comparatively, the integration of Thai culture shows that respondents were competent but relatively weaker, which means that it required specific intervention in the form of culturally responsive programs.

3.3 Multicultural Challenges

The study revealed that in terms of classroom management, respondents primarily struggled with clearly communicating classroom rules and eliciting effective responses to verbal cues. This challenge underscored the complexity of managing diverse classrooms where linguistic differences often hindered both effective communication and behavioral regulation (Winter, 2022). Such difficulties highlighted a significant barrier to establishing a conducive learning environment, as students may not have fully understood expectations or appropriately responded to instructions when these were delivered in an unfamiliar language (Mokiwa, 2020).

In terms of students' participation, the study shows that the primary challenges encountered by respondents were related to inviting students to express their ideas in English and promoting active participation in the classroom, which were largely impeded by language barriers. The results of the study emphasized the widespread nature of the language barrier as a detriment to student engagement, the restriction of free sharing of ideas, and the restriction of the formation of collaborative learning spaces (Fitriani et al., 2021), resulting in diminished responses by the students and classroom quietness (Nawamawat & Cedar, 2023; Uthai kun et al., 2021). This was further compounded by the fact that it is hard to articulate the answers of students so that they could meaningfully participate. Although the students might have tried to add something, the linguistic subtleties may misinterpret their meaning and thus decrease the abundance of classroom discussion (Pomat et al., 2024).

In terms of delivery of the lesson, the study shows that the most prominent challenges faced by the respondents were how they could make their lesson understandable without having to repeat themselves and how they could handle a perceived decrease in the quality of the lesson because of the language barriers. Due to the unfamiliarity of students with English, the necessity to rephrase something was important, and it was a continuous negotiation between linguistic accuracy and the effectiveness of the lesson, which can often interrupt the lessons and decrease the engagement of the students (Pomat et al., 2024). On the same note, the struggle to simplify language for improved comprehension underscored the profound impact of linguistic diversity on instructional competence, particularly in conveying complex scientific concepts (Wijayanti, 2024).

In terms of evaluating students' learning, the study shows that the most prevalent challenges were the lack of confidence of the student to request clarification and the ambiguity of the evaluation criteria because of the language barrier. These challenges formed a major barrier to the successful formative assessment and scaffolding of instruction, and they may have caused the low involvement of students because of language restrictions (Thongmak, 2022; Suwannatrai et al., 2022). In cases when students were not willing to ask for clarification, underlying misconceptions might have gone unexamined, whereas ambiguous assessment criteria undermined the validity and impartiality of assessment (Yassin et al., 2020). When linguistic obstacles undermined the performance of assessments, it might have led to inaccurate judgments about the competence of the student (Singh & Chowdhury, 2021).

The study also revealed that in terms of classroom expectations, the major challenges for respondents were their belief that Thai culture was hard to learn, and they could not easily adapt their expectations within the Thai context. According to Ma et al. (2022), these challenges were rooted in the non-existence of a systematic orientation of cultures. These results indicated that, although educators acknowledged the significance of cultural awareness of teaching efficacy, the real challenge of obtaining this knowledge and turning it into adaptive learning approaches was one of the daunting challenges (Pomat et al., 2024). As supported by Ainin et al. (2025), challenges in enacting culturally responsible teaching approaches may limit student engagement and undermine the usefulness in the classroom learning process.

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In terms of teaching approaches, the study shows that the top challenges faced by respondents were the inability to incorporate the local cultural material into the science classes and the inability to use the cultural background of the students during classroom sessions. According to Luangkrajang (2023), due to the inability to access training that is localized, teachers tend to fail to match the academic standards and culture of the schools. The results show that the application of culturally responsive pedagogy faced a considerable challenge because teachers continued to struggle with the successful integration of local contexts and backgrounds of students into the curriculum (Al et al., 2023). These difficulties were also associated with the insufficient training and resources that help teachers overcome cultural barriers in designing instruction (Pomat et al., 2024).

In terms of nonverbal cues, the study shows that the top challenges faced by respondents included identifying the meaning of common Thai nonverbal gestures in the classroom and responding to clarify the nonverbal feedback of the students. This was a major challenge in intercultural communication because the failure to understand nonverbal communication can cause misunderstandings and ineffective communication in classrooms (Williams et al., 2022). These findings show that teachers, during teaching, tend to modify their approach to learning by means of implementing multimodal techniques, including gestures, to overcome the linguistic barrier and achieve student-oriented learning (Zhou et al., 2025).

The study also revealed that in terms of job satisfaction, the top challenges included the lower level of satisfaction with the training opportunities provided and the feeling that professional development did not contribute to the development of teaching skills of the respondents. The offerings of professional development initiatives and the real needs of teachers to improve their teaching abilities show that they were not aligned (Cheng et al., 2024) and lacked an impact on teachers (Novio, 2021). These results were in line with studies that reveal some professional development programs were not contextually relevant and were insufficient to address the practical needs of teachers in multicultural and diverse learning environments around the world (Dadirai & Chauke, 2025).

In terms of motivation, top challenges indicated that respondents were neither motivated by the fact that their school supports them in lifelong learning nor by the fact that they are sure that professional growth contributed greatly to their confidence. According to Abacioglu et al. (2022), educators generally expressed low professional self-efficacy in dealing with diversity because of insufficient training in multicultural education. Likewise, in some cases, it was noted that although teachers can engage in professional development in order to optimize instructional strategies, they were not able to take full advantage of such opportunities due to barriers like time limitations, financial constraints, and high workloads, which in turn impacted their motivation and perceived effectiveness (Dayagbil & Alda, 2024).

In terms of retention, top challenges were the difficulty of building on previous training to upgrade teaching strategies and the difficulty of continuing to enhance the strategies obtained in the past training. The insufficient follow-up practices and qualifications of the faculty, as well as the lack of immediate training effectiveness measures, were factors that

impeded the ability of the teachers to retain and use the newly learned knowledge (Pojanapunya, 2024).

Overall, respondents show major challenges in language barriers, cultural adaptation, and professional development. In particular, the language barrier was the most prominent among all three issues; any small communication impediment could affect the classroom management, clarity of lessons, student engagement, and assessment validity. The results of these findings justified specific, proportionate intervention programs to minimize the language barrier in multicultural classrooms.

3.4 Test of significant difference

The study revealed that the type of school was the only variable that significantly differed in the level of instructional competence of the respondents, particularly on the use of the English language in teaching science. This shows that the capacity of teachers to teach science in English differed based on the school in which they were working. This finding aligned with other studies suggesting that educational context factors, including the kind of school, had a significant impact on teachers' competency (Cadiz-Gabejan, 2022). Specifically, it meant that educators in some school settings had more thorough training or were exposed to pedagogical strategies that boosted their effectiveness in English as a tool of teaching scientific concepts, which would affect their teaching effectiveness. Acera (2024) stated that this could have been due to variations in school resources, student demographics, or institutional policies that prioritized the development of the English language in science education in some schools.

Significant differences were also identified for job satisfaction, motivation, and retention when grouped according to the type of school. This implied that the kind of school affected the job satisfaction, motivation, and retention factors. This difference might have been due to differences in institutional support, availability of resources, or career growth opportunities provided in various types of schools, which, in aggregate, affected the overall well-being of teachers and their career life (Frianeza et al., 2024). Moreover, teacher satisfaction was reported to have a direct effect on teacher performance and commitment, with the implication that differences in the level of satisfaction between school types might have resulted in differences in educational quality (Izzati et al., 2023).

Additionally, there was a significant difference in classroom management when grouped according to their number of teaching experiences in a Thai school. This indicated that classroom management was mostly influenced by teaching experience in Thailand. It shows that the more time a teacher had been exposed to the Thai educational environment, the higher the probability of developing and executing the ability to effectively handle the diverse classroom dynamics, which was a subtle skill that could be shaped by the cultural and pedagogical peculiarities (Kang et al., 2020).

3.5 Test of significant relationship

The study revealed that the level of instructional competence had a moderate inverse relationship with the challenges encountered. The inverse relationship indicated that the higher the instructional competence, the lower the number of multicultural challenges. This implied that educators with a high level of knowledge of teaching methods and content delivery were in a better position to avoid and overcome the intricacies of handling different classroom environments. The greater the teaching proficiency, the easier it was to overcome the challenges posed by the diverse classroom arrangements (Maloloy-on & Arnando, 2023). The finding highlighted the relevance of specific professional development initiatives that not only enhanced the level of pedagogical knowledge but also directly developed the intercultural communication and cultural sensitivity of teachers (Ganesan & Morales, 2022). Furthermore, the inadequacy of instructional competence could have served to complicate the issues of multicultural classrooms, and continuing teacher training remained the key to success in navigating these dynamics (Setiawati et al., 2020).

4 Conclusion

Filipino science teachers in Thailand had a high competence level in using the English language and integration of current trends and pedagogy, but a moderate level of competence in incorporating Thai culture in teaching science.

The primary multicultural challenges faced by the respondents were language barriers impacting classroom management, student participation, delivery of the lesson, and evaluating students' learning. Followed by cultural adaptation issues concerning classroom expectations, teaching approaches, and non-verbal cues. Lastly, challenges related to professional development significantly affected their job satisfaction, motivation, and retention.

The significant difference between the use of the English language in science instruction and the type of school implied that various schools would probably offer different linguistic demands and support mechanisms that affected the ability of teachers to instruct in the English language. The significant difference between job satisfaction, motivation, and retention by the type of school indicated that the kind of school had a direct impact on the said and most important areas of professional well-being among Filipino science teachers. Furthermore, the significant difference between classroom management and the number of teaching experiences in Thai schools indicated that those teachers who have had many teaching experiences in Thai educational backgrounds might have a finer approach to keeping a well-organized and efficient learning process.

The moderate level of correlation observed between the instructional competence and multicultural issues highlighted the importance of special interventions to empower science teachers.

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